

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3888 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 108 – Part 1

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18205>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90 and 108. (for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different orders** — specifically orders 3 through 9 — each contributing a distinct structural layer. To bring order 108, order 9 is used twice.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 9 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8, first three are of equal-sums and last three are of different sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

The further study of multiple order bordered magic squares of orders 110, 120, 132 and 144 are given in details in the reference list.

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, **pandiagonal** magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White’s web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White’s web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90 and 108. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

- (b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

- (c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

- (a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

- (c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

- (b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

- (c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

- (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.
- (e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
- (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.
- (c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
- (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.
- (e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.
- (f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

- **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

- (a) The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.
- (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.
- (c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
- (d) The forth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.

- (e) The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9
- (f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

- **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

- (a) The first is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×3 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
- (b) The second is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. It contains again a **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 and of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
- (c) The third is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
- (d) The fourth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 5. The **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums in each case.
- (e) The fifth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 in the upper-left corner. The four **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 are of equal sums. Also the two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums.
- (f) The sixth is a **corner-type** magic square of order 9 formed by 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×9 and 2 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in upper-left corner. It is modified form of the **fifth-type** magic square.

Below summarises the six construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

- Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

- In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

- In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 72 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 90.
- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since the number 19940 is too high to handle, we worked with only 648 magic squares of order 90. This gives us $6 \times 648 = 3888$ magic squares of order 108.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.90}} = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 6 \times 6 = 19940. \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 7th border of magic squares of order 9. See the details below.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 108

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 108, we shall use the following six different types of magic squares of order 9 over the magic square of order 90 as an upper border magic squares resulting in magic squares of order 108. These six magic square are different from the six magic square considered in upper border of order 90.

9	mgc									369	9	mgc									369
8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369	8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369		
1	20	46	60	48	31	29	53	81	369	1	42	37	44	46	36	24	58	81	369		
3	62	36	22	34	51	25	57	79	369	3	43	41	39	49	33	28	54	79	369		
5	50	32	42	37	44	33	49	77	369	5	38	45	40	30	52	64	18	77	369		
73	58	24	43	41	39	63	19	9	369	73	50	48	47	29	31	61	21	9	369		
71	59	23	38	45	40	55	27	11	369	71	32	34	35	51	53	26	56	11	369		
69	17	65	64	28	35	52	26	13	369	69	62	65	23	63	22	27	25	13	369		
67	21	61	18	54	47	30	56	15	369	67	20	17	59	19	60	57	55	15	369		
72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369	72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369		
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369		

9	mgc									369	9	mgc									369
8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369	8	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	15	67	369	
1	63	54	27	31	30	53	29	81	369	1	17	42	37	44	46	36	65	14	68	369	
3	19	28	55	51	52	22	60	79	369	3	19	43	41	39	49	33	63	80	2	369	
5	50	32	44	39	40	46	36	77	369	5	59	38	45	40	30	52	23	10	72	369	
73	35	47	37	41	45	26	56	9	369	73	57	50	48	47	29	31	25	8	74	369	
71	23	59	42	43	38	58	24	11	369	71	55	32	34	35	51	53	27	77	5	369	
69	33	49	20	65	61	25	34	13	369	69	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	81	1	369	
67	64	18	62	17	21	57	48	15	369	67	78	79	16	13	75	76	12	11	9	369	
72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369	72	4	3	66	69	7	6	70	73	71	369	
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369		

9	mgc									369	9	mgc									369
	20	46	60	48	31	29	53	67	15	369		29	35	41	47	53	58	24	54	28	369
	62	36	22	34	51	25	57	3	79	369		46	52	33	34	40	72	10	7	75	369
	50	32	42	37	44	33	49	5	77	369		38	39	45	51	32	3	79	77	5	369
	58	24	43	41	39	63	19	73	9	369		50	31	37	43	44	6	76	4	78	369
	59	23	38	45	40	55	27	71	11	369		42	48	49	30	36	66	16	63	19	369
	17	65	64	35	28	52	26	69	13	369		61	13	14	18	55	71	8	73	56	369
	21	61	18	47	54	30	56	1	81	369		21	69	68	64	27	11	74	9	26	369
	16	80	78	76	75	12	14	8	10	369		15	60	81	20	59	25	12	17	80	369
	66	2	4	6	7	70	68	72	74	369		67	22	1	62	23	57	70	65	2	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.
 1. The first is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×3 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
 2. The second is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. It contains again a **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 and of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
 3. The third is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
 4. The forth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 5. The **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums in each case.
 5. The fifth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 in the upper-left corner. The four **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 are of equal sums. Also the two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums.
 6. The sixth is a **corner-type** magic square of order 9 formed by 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×9 and 2 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in upper-left corner. It is modified form of the **fifth-type** magic square.

Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since this number is too high, we worked with 648 magic squares of order 90, resulting in 3888 magic square of order 108.

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3888 magic squares of order 108 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 9. More details are in an excel file attached with the work.

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